

DEVELOPMENT OF COMPUTER VISION TRAINING SOFTWARE IN ICT

Allaberganova Muyassar Rimberganovna

teacher of Urgench branch of TUIT

amuyassar83@gmail.com

Gulimova Zilola Shuxratovna

2nd year student of academic lyceum of

Urganch State University

Abstract: The article discusses the didactic potential for the use of a modern multimedia textbook as software, as an auxiliary visual means of teaching computer graphics. the article gives instructions and suggestions for teaching and popularization of the subject of computer graphics on the basis of modern electronic textbooks and their use.

Key words: Information technologies, computer graphics, raster, vector, fractal graphics, learn graph, image, object, animation, 2D and 3D graphics, modern electronic textbooks.

In the world, special attention is paid to the technologicalization of teaching processes, the achievement of effective teaching and learning through information and communication technologies, the introduction of quality management paradigms. Given the role and importance of natural and exact sciences, including computer graphics, in higher education, there is a tendency to use the features of project-based approaches based on the block-module system as an innovative form of teacher training[2].

Reforms in our country to ensure the integration of science, education and industry, the development of higher education, strengthening the material and technical base, improving the forms and content of education expand the opportunities for the

introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process. At the same time, there is a lack of systematic approaches to improving the effectiveness of training of future teachers of computer graphics, a mechanism to ensure the positive effectiveness of the training of "Computer Graphics". The Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan identifies priorities such as "continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market, improving the quality of education in higher education, in-depth study of important and demanding subjects such as computer graphics" [1]. In this regard, it is important to define a modern concept of designing the subject "Computer Graphics" in higher education, innovative modeling of teaching technology, improving the methodological support[3].

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", PF-5635 of January 17, 2019 "Strategy of actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021" Decree "On the State Program for the Year of Active Investment and Social Development", No. PQ2909 of April 20, 2017 "On measures for further development of the higher education system", PQ of July 27, 2017 Resolution No. 3151 "On measures to further expand the participation of industries and sectors of the economy in improving the quality of higher education" and the program "Learn Graph" created in the framework of this study in the implementation of the tasks set out in the regulations of this activity a certain level of service does[4,5].

U.Madaminov on the study of methodological aspects (content, purpose, methods and tools) of the disciplines taught in higher education institutions in the field of pedagogical education, problems aimed at teaching computer graphics and the development of educational projects, B.Boltaev, M.Ziyakhodjaev, N.Taylakov, A.Hayitov, U.Yuldashev, R.Bakiev, M.Mamarajabov, A.Siddikov and others carried out scientific researches, and CIS scientists Y.Gursky, K.Grebennikov, L.Ivannikova,

O.Krainova, O.Odintsova, N.Petrova, E.Tretyakova, L.Turanova reviewed in their works [6,7].

Based on the above, we can say that today computer graphics is one of the most rapidly evolving areas of modern information technology. Such development is taking place both in the field of hardware and software. They allow you to create video, multimedia products, moving images. Such software products are advertising tools and are used in the field of art and multimedia technology. In addition, great attention is paid to the presentation graphics, geometric modeling, design of graphical interfaces, animation and the creation of visible moving objects[8].

We can create graphic objects in programming languages or in ready-made special programs. The key is how realistic the image is. The appearance of an object, the harmony of its colors, and the size of the image all indicate the importance of computer graphics. Computer graphics is taught as a separate subject in secondary special and higher education institutions on the basis of a special plan. This, in turn, requires the development of computer graphics software. There are several such software products available today. However, such programs focus less on offline and online learning, communication, and competition. Only one user can learn the program independently, but if the program is used by several users, ie in groups in schools or universities, with their own login and password, it will increase the effectiveness of reading and studying the textbook. That's why we created Leran Graph, taking into account the above-mentioned shortcomings[9].

This program was developed on the basis of the science program based on Annex 2 to the Order of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 27, 2018 No. 274. The program is designed primarily for university students and independent users. The program consists of 17 textbooks, theoretical and practical assignments, a forum with users and a graphical view of the results. The program basically consists of 5 windows. It consists of a program login window, a key entry window, a login and password activation window, a registration window, and a program main window [10] (Figure 1).

After installing the program, a special code will be issued, to activate the program, this code will be captured, sent by telegram to the phone number specified in

Figure 1. Registration window. the program, and you will be given a special code by the admin.

You can only use the code once, ie when you uninstall and reinstall the program, the previous activation code will not work. After activating the code, you need to register to use the program. As mentioned above, the program can be used as a group, and each has its own dialog box and its own results.

After logging in to the program with a login and password, a list of information and lessons relevant to you will appear (Figure 3). Languages such as html, css, javascript, mysql, java were used to ensure the dynamics of the program, to attract the learner, to leave an impression on each topic and to ensure efficiency.

Figure 3. Main window

Figure 3. Key activation window.

The program itself was developed in the JavaFX programming language. Generalized and in-depth topics for teaching computer graphics in the program and types of computer graphics: raster, vector, fractal graphics

additional information are provided (Figure 4).

topshiriqlar.

Computers have a thorough understanding of graphics and the knowledge and skills to create raster, vector, and fractal images in graphic editors [11].

We will continue to get acquainted with the program. Students can test the knowledge and skills they are learning through the program (Figure 5).

student is Figure 5. Test performance window

1st interval If the test works but the

result is not satisfactory, it tries to process it and tries to get the result high and enter it into the program database. The program prevents these cases, and the results of the processed test are not stored in the database. These processes work the same way for all tests.

details, case studies, assignments, and

In addition, the sequence of working with graphic editors for each type of graphics, the creation of 2- and 3-dimensional images is described in detail.

The learners of the program are

4-rasm. Amaliy mavzular va

There is also a separate section for students and users to view and analyze their results, which creates competition between users of the program and increases their interest in science and the lesson [12, 13] (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Graphical representation of user results.

Students learn science through the program, and in the process, they may have questions and misunderstandings on topics[14]. In this regard, the student first sees the user rating of the program and can ask the user who is higher, which in turn is the basis

for working as a group among students. The program has a Forum section for interaction, where you can ask general questions[15]. (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Forum window.

The research carried out by the author will allow us to create a “ Learn Graph ”tool environment that provides support for the formation of skills in solving computer graphics problems, contributing to an increase in the effectiveness of the learning process of computer graphics.

In short, the use of this "Learn Graph" program in the educational process will increase the effectiveness of education, improve students' new knowledge and skills. Students will be able to work independently on the subject of computer graphics, and if the subject is taught using the program, the human factor will not interfere in the assessment of students. The instrumental environment learn graph is implemented in the educational process at Urgench branch of Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al Khwarizmi and is used in the study of the course "computer graphics".

REFERENCES

1. Madaminov Uktamjon Ataxanovich, Mamatqulov Mirjalol Saminjon o'g'li. Ma'lumotlar tuzilmasi va algoritmlari. Innovations in technology and science education. Vol. 2, Issue 9. 05/2023, 10-16.
2. Madaminov Uktamjon Ataxanovich, Bayramova Shohida Dilshodbek qizi. Zamonaviy web texnologiyalar yordamida multimediali web ilova ishlab chiqish. Innovations in technology and science education. Vol. 2, Issue 9. 05/2023, 17-24.
3. Madaminov Uktamjon Ataxanovich, Karimova Mumtozbegin Sobirboy qizi. Oliy ta'lim tashkilotlarida web dasturlashni o'rgatuvchi amaliy loyiha ishlab chiqish. Innovations in technology and science education. Vol. 2, Issue 9. 05/2023, 25-30.
4. Madaminov Uktamjon Ataxanovich, Bektemirova Risolat Shukurla qizi. Python dasturlash tili. Innovations in technology and science education. Vol. 2, Issue 9. 05/2023, 31-36.
5. Madaminov Uktamjon Ataxanovich, Qalandarova Kamola Shermat qizi. Ta'limda zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalar va ulardan foydalanishni o'rgatuvchi elektron resurs ishlab chiqish. Innovations in technology and science education. Vol. 2, Issue 9. 05/2023, 37-42.

6. Madaminov Uktamjon Ataxanovich, Abdalova Xilola Botirovna. Web dasturlashni o'rgatuvchi mobil ilova ishlash chiqish texnologiyasi. Innovations in technology and science education. Vol. 2, Issue 9. 05/2023, 43-49.
7. U.A. Madaminov, O.K. Ataboev, D.R. Kodirov, M.N. Jumaniyazov. JAVA DASTURLASH MUHITIDA SHART OPERATORLARI (IF, SWITCH CASE). ORIENTAL RENAISSANCE: INNOVATIVE, EDUCATIONAL, NATURAL AND SOCIAL SCIENCES. VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 5. 2022/5. 1203-1208 p.
8. U.A. Madaminov, D.R. Kodirov, E.D. Jolimbetova. VIZUAL DASTURLASH YORDAMIDA AMALIY MASALALARNI YECHISH. TA'LIM FIDOYILARI. Vol.1, Issue 1. 2022/6. 77-85.
9. Madaminov Uktamjon Ataxanovich, Qodirov Davronbek Rajabboy o'g'li, Avezov Mardonbek Abdullayevich. Use of visit karakalpakstan mobile app in the development of tourism in the republic of karakalpakstan. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON HUMAN COMPUTING STUDIES. 2021. p-ISSN: 2615-1898. Volume: 03 Issue: 8. 13-17 p.
10. Madaminov Uktamjon Ataxanovich, Urazboyev Kamolbek Ulugbek o'g'li. A Program Which Can Teach Students about Java Program Language And Its Functions. International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology. Vol. 8, Issue 10, 2021/10. 2350-0328.
11. Allaberganova Muyassar Rimberganovna Madaminov Uktamjon Ataxanovich, Kutliyev Sardor Pulatovich, Avezov Mardonbek Abdullayevich, O'razboyev Nurbek Ulug'bek o'g'li. Methodology of electronic educational resources creation and use of applications. International Journal of Applied Research 2020; 6(6): 133-135.
12. Uktamjon Ataxanovich Madaminov. [Zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda pedagogik o'lchov me'zonlari elementlari va](#)

[ulardan foydalanish uslubiyatini o'rganish](#). «ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И НАУКА В XXI ВЕКЕ». 2023/6/3.

13. Madaminov Uktamjon, Davronbek Qodirov, Razzoqova Zarina, Sheripbaev Shaxriyor, Embergenov Sabir. Madaminov Uktamjon, Davronbek Qodirov, Razzoqova Zarina, Sheripbaev Shaxriyor, Embergenov Sabir. Innovations in Technology and Science Education. 2023/6/3. 807-812 p.

14. Madaminov Uktamjon. [Elektron ta'lim resurlarini yaratish va amaliy dasturlardan foydalanish metodikasi](#). Innovations in Technology and Science Education. 2023, 817-826 p.

15. Uktam Madaminov Ataxanovich, Davronbek Qodirov Rajabboy o'g'li. [Creating an application for training science](#). Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2023, 295-300p.